

CHARGE AND STABILITY OF COLLOIDS. PART III. POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATIONS OF FERRIC HYDROXIDE SOL

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The discrepancy in the results of Rabinowitch and Weiser in the amounts of the counter-ions released on adding precipitating ions of varying valency to a ferric hydroxide sol has been investigated. It has been proved that the amount of the counter-ions released from a sol of ferric hydroxide depends on the purity of the sol. The quantity of the released chlorine from a ferric hydroxide sol gets smaller and smaller as the purity of the sol is increased by progressive dialysis. In the case of more impure sols the chlorine released is super-equivalent, whereas with increase of purity the quantity released is less than the chlorine equivalent of the added electrolyte.

Recently the mechanism of electrolyte coagulation of hydrophobic colloids has been studied by following the displacement of the counter-ions. Pauli (*Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1923, 17, 256) used potentiometric titration method and has shown that in a ferric hydroxide sol, more and more of chlorine is set free on adding increasing quantity of the electrolyte. He measured the concentration of chlorine only at the end of the process, but Rabinowitsch and Kargin (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, 133, 203) measured the chlorine concentration not only at the end but during the process of coagulation. They found that super-equivalent amount of chlorine is released on adding electrolytes. Weiser (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 1) allowed the sol and electrolyte mixtures to remain in contact for 24 hours before proceeding with the titrations. He used nitrate, sulphate, citrate and ferricyanide. In all these cases he found the displaced chlorine to be always less than the amount of the electrolyte added when expressed in chlorine equivalent.

It has been pointed out by Dhar (Dhar and co-workers, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 31 ; 1932, 9, 315, ; 1933, 10, 471) that the physical properties of a sol depend considerably on its purity. They have shown that if a sol contains a considerable amount of stabilising electrolyte it may behave abnormally on dilution, while a purer sample of it behaves normally. This means that the constitution of a sol changes with purity.

In view of the above the discrepancy in the observations of Rabinowitsch (*loc. cit.*) and Weiser (*loc. cit.*) appears ultimately to lie in the purity of the sol. It has been the object of this series of papers to estimate the amount of chlorine expelled from a sol of ferric hydroxide which was subjected to progressive dialysis.

EXPERIMENTAL

Kahlbaum's ferric chloride (100 g.) was dissolved in freshly distilled water and diluted to about 4 litres. Dilute ammonia was added drop by drop, and after each addition of the drop of ammonia, the solution was thoroughly shaken. This process continued till the sol was just short of precipitation. The sol was filtered next day. A portion of the sol was set apart for potentiometric titrations from the original sol and the rest was kept for dialysis. Samples of sol were taken out from the dialysers after every sixth day. The concentrations of the original sol as well as those obtained by subsequent dialysis and the chlorine content of each sample were determined by the usual methods. A potentiometric method exactly similar to that of Weiser (*loc. cit.*) was used in order to avoid the uncertainty that may be present in Rabinowitsch's method.

TABLE I
Sol I

Conc. of Fe_2O_3 sol = 8.04 g./litre. Chlorine content = 0.312 g. ions/litre. *Purity of the sol. = 25.8. Temp. = 25°

N-KNO ₃ added.	(volt). $\bar{x}$	[Cl] × 10 ³		Total.	equiv. to [NO ₃] added.	IN/100 K ₂ SO ₄ added.	(volt). $\bar{x}$	[Cl] × 10 ³		Total.	equiv. to [NO ₃] added.	(N/100) K-citrate added. (volt). $\bar{x}$	[Cl] × 10 ³		Total.	equiv. to [citrate] added.	
		$\bar{x}$ eq1 × 10 ³ .	disp. laced.					$\bar{x}$ eq1 × 10 ³ .	disp. laced.				$\bar{x}$ eq1 × 10 ³ .	disp. laced.			$\bar{x}$ eq1 × 10 ³ .
0.0 c.c.	0.0043	67.16	83.34	0.00	0.0	0.0 c.c.	0.0043	67.16	83.34	0.00	0.0	0.0 c.c.	0.0043	67.16	83.34	0.00	0.0
0.8	0.0041	67.68	84.28	0.94	40	0.4	0.0036	69.02	86.04	2.70	1.0	2.0	0.0035	69.28	86.26	2.82	1.0
1.6	0.0036	69.02	86.04	2.70	80	0.8	0.0027	71.47	89.33	5.99	2.0	4.0	0.0028	71.19	89.00	5.66	2.0
2.4	0.0031	70.37	87.97	4.63	120	1.2	0.0020	73.29	91.85	8.51	3.0	6.0	0.0022	72.89	91.23	7.89	3.0
3.2	0.0028	71.19	89.00	5.66	160	1.6	0.0015	74.89	93.95	10.61	4.0	8.0	0.0018	74.04	92.89	9.55	4.0
4.0	0.0024	72.32	90.53	7.19	200	2.0	0.0012	77.09	96.85	13.51	5.0	10.0	0.0013	75.47	94.83	11.49	5.0

TABLE II
Sol III.

Conc. of Fe_2O_3 sol = 7.36 g./litre. Chlorine content = 0.041 g. ions/litre. Purity of the sol = 179.5. Temp. = 25°.

N-KNO ₃ added.	(volt). $\bar{x}$	[Cl] × 10 ³		Total.	equiv. to [NO ₃] added.	IN/200 K ₂ SO ₄ added.	(volt). $\bar{x}$	[Cl] × 10 ³		Total.	equiv. to [NO ₃] added.	(N/100) K-citrate added. (volt). $\bar{x}$	[Cl] × 10 ³		Total.	equiv. to [citrate] added.	
		$\bar{x}$ eq1 × 10 ³ .	disp. laced.					$\bar{x}$ eq1 × 10 ³ .	disp. laced.				$\bar{x}$ eq1 × 10 ³ .	disp. laced.			$\bar{x}$ eq1 × 10 ³ .
0.0 c.c.	0.0333	21.71	24.54	0.00	0	0.0 c.c.	0.0333	21.71	24.54	0.00	0	0.0 c.c.	0.0333	21.71	24.54	0.00	0.0 c.c.
0.4	0.0329	22.05	24.96	0.42	20	0.2	0.0326	22.32	25.30	0.76	0.5	2.0	0.0323	22.58	25.62	1.08	1.0
0.8	0.0327	22.22	25.16	0.62	40	0.4	0.0329	22.93	26.02	1.48	1.0	4.0	0.0314	23.77	26.65	2.11	2.0
1.2	0.0321	22.75	25.79	1.25	60	0.6	0.0311	23.65	26.87	2.33	1.5	5.0	0.0309	23.84	27.24	2.70	2.5
1.6	0.0317	23.11	26.22	1.68	80	1.0	0.0292	25.46	29.10	4.36	2.5	6.0	0.0304	24.31	27.81	3.27	3.0
2.0	0.0313	23.47	26.67	2.13	125	1.4	0.0278	26.89	30.92	6.38	3.5	8.0	0.0298	24.87	28.50	3.96	4.0

* Purity of the sol signifies the ratio $[\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3]/[\text{Cl}]$ in all the tables.

TABLE III

Sol IV

Conc. of Fe_2O_3 sol. = 6.85 g./litre. Chlorine content = 0.035 g. ions/litre. Purity = 274.0 Temp. = 25°

(N/100) K-citrate added.	$\bar{\pi}$ (volt).	$\bar{\pi}$ $\text{Cl} \times 10^3$.	[Cl] $\times 10^3$		(N/20) K ₂ SO ₄ added.	$\bar{\pi}$ (volt).	$\bar{\pi}$ $\text{Cl} \times 10^3$.	[Cl] $\times 10^3$		N:KNO ₃ added.	$\bar{\pi}$ (volt).	$\bar{\pi}$ $\text{Cl} \times 10^3$.	[Cl] $\times 10^3$		equiv. to [NO ₃] added.		
			Total.	disp. laced.				Total.	disp. laced.				Total.	disp. laced.		Total.	disp. laced.
0.0 c.c.	0.0728	4.66	5.01	0.06	0.00	0.0 c.c.	0.0728	4.66	5.01	0.00	0.0 c.c.	0.0728	4.66	5.01	0.00	0.0	
1.0	0.0720	5.00	5.37	0.36	0.50	0.4	0.0702	5.16	5.55	0.54	0.50	0.4	0.0728	4.89	5.71	0.20	20.0
2.0	0.0695	5.30	5.71	0.70	1.00	0.4	0.0690	5.41	5.84	0.83	1.00	0.8	0.0706	5.08	5.46	0.45	40.0
3.0	0.0678	5.67	6.11	1.10	1.50	0.6	0.0654	6.22	6.72	1.17	1.50	1.2	0.0699	5.22	5.83	0.62	60.0
5.0	0.0666	5.93	6.41	1.40	2.00	0.9	0.0640	6.57	7.12	2.11	2.25	1.6	0.0684	5.33	5.97	0.96	80.0
7.0	0.0652	6.27	6.78	1.77	3.50	1.3	0.0611	7.35	7.99	3.98	3.25	2.4	0.0668	6.12	6.62	1.61	120.0

TABLE IV

Sol VI

Sol. conc. = 6.46 g./litre. Chlorine content = 0.01 g. ions/litre. Purity = 646.0. Temp. = 25°

N:KNO ₃ added.	$\bar{\pi}$ (volt).	$\bar{\pi}$ $\text{Cl} \times 10^3$.	[Cl] $\times 10^3$		(N/20) K ₂ SO ₄ added.	$\bar{\pi}$ (volt).	$\bar{\pi}$ $\text{Cl} \times 10^3$.	[Cl] $\times 10^3$		(N/200) K-citrate added.	$\bar{\pi}$ (volt).	$\bar{\pi}$ $\text{Cl} \times 10^3$.	[Cl] $\times 10^3$		equiv. to [citrate] added.		
			Total.	disp. laced.				Total.	disp. laced.				Total.	disp. laced.		Total.	disp. laced.
0.0 c.c.	0.1065	1.26	1.28	0.00	0	0.0 c.c.	0.1065	1.26	1.28	0.00	0.0 c.c.	0.1065	1.26	1.28	0.00	0.0	
0.2	0.0968	1.83	1.88	0.60	1.0	0.2	0.0963	1.87	1.91	0.63	0.50	1.0	0.0995	1.65	1.66	0.40	0.5
0.4	0.0920	2.21	2.27	0.99	2.0	0.4	0.0936	2.08	2.14	0.86	1.00	2.0	0.0985	1.72	1.76	0.46	1.0
0.6	0.0910	2.50	2.57	1.09	3.0	0.6	0.0913	2.27	2.35	1.07	1.50	3.0	0.0920	2.21	2.27	0.99	1.5
1.2	0.0902	3.37	3.45	1.17	6.0	0.8	0.0875	3.63	3.74	1.46	2.00	4.0	0.0900	2.39	2.46	1.16	2.0
1.6	0.0885	3.53	3.63	1.35	8.0	1.1	0.0847	3.93	3.99	1.81	2.75	6.0	0.0870	2.68	2.78	1.50	3.0

Potentiometric titrations were done by taking 10 c.c. of the sol of a particular sample in several stoppered bottles and to these were added electrolytes in varying concentrations starting from a certain minimum up to the coagulating concentration in a regular increasing order. The total volume of the sol and the electrolyte in each case was made up to 20 c.c. by adding the requisite amount of water to the electrolyte. The sol and the water-electrolyte mixtures were added uniformly so as to avoid any localised coagulation. Finally the sol-electrolyte mixtures were thoroughly shaken. To each of these bottles were added small doses of a pure sample of calomel, and the mixtures were left over for 24 hours to attain equilibrium. In a half element was placed the sol-electrolyte mixture, using platinum electrode which dipped in freshly distilled mercury, and the other half element was $N/10$ -calomel electrode. The nozzles of both these half elements dipped in a vessel containing $N/10$ -KCl solution.

A modified form of Nernst equation was used to calculate the activity of the displaced chlorine. This calculated value of the activity was converted into molar concentration by dividing it by the activity coefficient as read off from the graph obtained from the data of Lewis and Randall (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 1132). The amount of the electrolyte added is expressed in terms of the equivalent amount of chlorine. The results obtained with samples of different purity of the sol (purity signifies the ratio: Fe_2O_3 to Cl) are tabulated below and shown graphically in Figs. 1 and 2 with KNO_3 and K_2SO_4 only. For economy of space, the figure with K-citrate is not given but it is similar to Fig. 2 with K_2SO_4 .

DISCUSSION

From the above results it is clear that with the same sol the quantity of the displaced chlorine gets smaller and smaller as the sol becomes purer and purer even when the displaced chlorine is measured by one and the same method.

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

In the following table is given the relation between purity and the amount of chlorine displaced for the sols used in this paper (Table V). Detailed results of some of these are not given in order to economise space but the results obtained are plotted in Figs. 1 and 2.

TABLE V

Sol.	Amount of Fe_2O_3 (g./litre).	Chlorine (g. mol./litre).	Purity	Nature of Cl displaced.
I	8.04	0.312	25.8	Super-equiv.
II	7.54	0.095	79.4	"
III	7.36	0.047	179.5	"
IV	6.85	0.025	274.0	< Equiv.
V	6.68	0.018	372.9	"
VI	6.46	0.010	646.0	"
VII	6.08	0.0085	715.4	"

TABLE VI

Sol.	Author.	Fe_2O_3 (g./litre).	Cl (g. mol./litre).	Purity.	Nature of Cl displaced
I	Rabinowitsch	8.71	—	—	—
II	"	5.76	0.0254	226.8	Super-equiv.
III	Weiser	6.46	0.0158	408.7	< Equiv.
IV	"	6.92	0.0166	416.9	"
V	"	4.08	0.0047	868.2	"

It is interesting to compare Table V with the one obtained from the results published by Rabinowitsch (*loc. cit.*) and Weiser (*loc. cit.*) as given in Table VI.

From Table VI it will be apparent that all the sols used by Weiser had a purity greater than the purity of the sol which begins to release chlorine ions less than the added quantity of the coagulating ions in the experiments recorded in the present communication.

From Table V it is clear that the sol used here behaves exactly in a similar manner to that of Weiser's as soon as it reaches a purity of 274.0, whereas sols of lesser purity release super-equivalent amounts of chlorine like that observed by Rabinowitsch.

It has been pointed out by Rabinowitsch that ageing of the sol also plays an important part. A more aged sol was observed by him to release a super-equivalent amount of chlorine. This behaviour very much resembles the behaviour of the impure sols used in this paper.

In sols of different degrees of purity used in this paper, a considerable amount of KNO_3 was necessary to effect coagulation but the released chlorine was considerably less than the added electrolyte (*cf.* Weiser, *loc. cit.*). Evidently the relation between the amount of chlorine released depends on the valency of the precipitating ion apart from the purity and the age of the sol.

The results with KNO_3 have been plotted in Fig. 1. From the curves it is apparent that the form bears a similarity to the form of the curves obtained with K_2SO_4 in Fig. 2. There is no real difference between the various curves. Weiser (*loc. cit.*) remarked that 'the form of the curve with KNO_3 was distinctly different from that for salts with multivalent precipitating ions'. Evidently the present work does not justify this. Weiser's statement is correct only when the purity of the sol is very high. (*cf.* curves for sols V, IV and VII and the one obtained with Weiser's sol I).

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